

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

<https://llrjournal.com/index.php/11>

**THE IMPORTANCE OF AI (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE) IN
LEARNING OF ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE AT DISTRICT
SHANGLA KHYBER PAKHTUNKHWA PAKISTAN**

**Majid Ali Khan^{*1}, Said Hussain Shah², Wajid Ullah³,
Ishaq Ali⁴**

*^{*1}Lecturer in English, Department of English, University
of Shangla*

*²English Linguistics and Applied Linguistics, School of
Foreign Languages, Chengdu University of Technology,
China*

*^{3,4}BS Student, Department of English, University of
Shangla*

*^{*1}majidalikhaan@gmail.com,*

²hussainkhan5828@gmail.com,

³khattakw512@gmail.com, ⁴is2964650@gmail.com

²<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-2936-1047>

Abstract

This study explores the importance of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in learning of English as a second language (ESL) among university students in District Shangla, KPK, Pakistan. The research aims to analyze the role of AI, identify its benefits and challenges, and examine how students use AI tools like (ChatGPT, DeepSeek, Gemini, Perplexity and Meta AI) for language learning. A qualitative approach was used, with data collected through structured interviews involving 12 ESL learners. Thematic analysis revealed key findings. Students found AI tools accessible and user-friendly, helping them learn anytime and anywhere. These tools improved skills like vocabulary, reading, and writing, though speaking and listening received less focus. AI also increased motivation by providing instant feedback and interactive features. However, challenges were noted. Students emphasized that AI cannot replace teachers due to its lack of emotional intelligence and real-life experience. Concerns about data privacy, confusing responses, and reliance on internet connectivity were also raised. Despite these issues, participants viewed AI as a valuable supplement to traditional learning. Recommendations include developing offline AI tools, ensuring data privacy, and integrating AI into classroom activities while maintaining teacher guidance. Policymakers should promote equitable access to digital resources, especially in rural areas. In conclusion, AI enhances ESL learning by making it flexible and engaging, but it works best alongside human instruction. Future research should explore AI role in speaking and listening skills and address accessibility challenges. This study provides insights for educators, developers, and policymakers to optimize AI use in language education.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, Second language Learning, ESL, language skills and AI tools.*

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence has become an important part of modern life. In technological progress is inevitable and continues to shape our daily experiences. Science and technology advance hand in hand, as scientific methods provide a logical framework grounded in theory and evidence. This enables continuous development (Absari et al, 2020). Technological innovations have opened avenues for acquiring knowledge and skills that are practical and applicable. Furthermore, these technological influences extend into industrial sectors, where they have shared transformative changes (Kirana et al, 2024). In today era of technological change, AI in education has become one of the most striking examples of invention. It is reshaping the way people learn and tech. The innovation of technology in the recent past has contributed tremendously in various segments of human life, with education having been the most affected. AI demonstrated an ability to transform the several industries including education (Young et al., 2022). There is a transformation of the learning process in the learning environment where AI tools are personalizing, efficient and effective. An example is the adaptive learning platform which can tailor education content to suit the unique needs of any learner. In addition, AI-driven tools can give immediate feedback on multiple abilities, including writing and pronunciation, which is helpful in coping with the problems frequently arising in conventional classrooms (Chen et al., 2020). The use of AI in education is slowly gaining momentum in Pakistan, providing novel opportunities to help teachers and the students achieve better learning results. As education continues to change, learning how to use AI has become an important skill. Both students and teachers need it to grow and succeed. AI literacy requires a fresh way of thinking. It means having the right skills to work well with both people and machines. This includes the ability to understand, judge, and use AI tools in a safe and responsible way (Long & Magerko, 2020). In today's changing education system, students must keep improving their digital skills to match the speed of technology. They need to be ready for a future that is hard to predict. In modern classrooms, AI tools help students examine AI-generated content with a critical eye. These tools also help them become confident and smart users of technology. AI can support teachers too, as it provides instant feedback and useful data. This helps teachers improve their teaching methods, especially when guiding students in Reading, Writing, Listening and Speaking in a second language. In English second language learning, AI creates fresh Chances for progress. It reshapes the method of both learners and teachers. The combination of the English language learning and Artificial Intelligence (AI) is presenting new and very effective teaching strategies in English

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

language to non-native speakers. Today, many apps and online platforms use AI technology to support students in learning English. These platforms are interactive, allowing students to take part actively in their learning. They give instant feedback, so learners can quickly understand their mistakes and improve. Moreover, the learning paths are flexible; they change according to the progress of a given student and his or her particular needs (Lee, 2020). This enables learners to study in a manner and pace that is most suitable for them. These AI-based tools also make learning more engaging and enjoyable, which keeps students motivated. Another benefit is that these tools can track the learner's improvement over time, making it easier for both students and teachers to see what areas need more focus. All these new ways of learning are very helpful in understanding how students learn languages in different situations, such as in classrooms, at home, or online. However, there are times when these tools can also create problems. For example, using too many digital tools at once might distract students or reduce their focus in class. Such distractions as talking, communicative social media and multi-app usage can easily interfere with the actual learning (Ryan et al., 2021). The same rule applies to AI in English language learning: it works best when used with clear purpose and in moderation. The value of Artificial Intelligence in learning English as second or foreign language is acquiring increasing relevance. Duolingo, Grammarly, ELSA Speak, and other language learning tools are growing popular among learners as they help significantly in other language skills, including Grammar correction, vocabulary enhancement and pronunciation practice. These applications provide flexible access to learning material and delivers immediate feedback, which greatly improve the efficiency of language acquisitions and learning. For Examples, Grammarly is used to help learners by correcting grammar and enhancing writing style in real time, while ELSA speak specializes in precise pronunciation correction through instant targeted feedback. Duolingo combines gamified lessons to engage users in grammar, vocabulary, speaking and listening exercises by adapting to individual learning needs and providing personalized practice. These AI tools promote autonomous and interactive language learning that can be accessed anytime and anywhere. This enhances learner engagement and outcomes (Huang et al, 2021). AI helps improve thinking skills, supports creativity, saves resources, and improves teaching methods (Jingshan, 2023). Machine learning (ML) and Natural language processing (NLP) allow the individualization of the learning experience with its applications. They also automate their repetitive activities, provide feedback on tasks, and identify the areas where learners need improvement (Hinojo-Lucena et al., 2019). The use of breakthrough AI in education is gradually dislodging traditional ways of teaching, as lessons are adjusted lessons to fit each student's needs (Chang et al., 2022). In language learning, AI speech tools help students improve speaking skills (Zou et al., 2023). AI can also understand speech and support new methods such the flipped classroom. This shows how AI can change the way languages are taught and learned (Moulieswaran & Kumar, 2023). Additionally, in higher education, the role of AI is even more powerful as it allows students to interact with computers in new ways, even though thoughts. This point to major changes in the future of universities (Popenici & Kerr, 2017).

Despite these benefits, it is also important to look at the changes and Limits of AI in education. Additionally, the context of education AI has many benefits, but there are some problems with using it. Some people worry about depending on technology, keeping personal data and losing the creativity of human interaction in learning. AI is very important, but if students understand it. If we can learn and work well and what does and does not help, these are batter tools for students to truly and effectively learn. The present study of The Importance of Artificial Intelligence in Learning of English as a Second Language at district Shangla Khyber Pakhtoon Khwa Pakistan focuses on the application of multiple AI-based instruments that are used for language learning, such as (ChatGPT, DeepSeek, Gemini, perplexity, Meta AI and Google Translate) which are changing the learning experience. The goal is a better understanding of AI supported language learning and the factor effect its use and success.

Research Problem

The increasing use of Artificial Intelligence is affecting how English as a Second Language (ESL) students in Pakistan develop their reading, writing, listening and speaking abilities. AI tools (ChatGPT, DeepSeek, Gemini, Perplexity, and Meta AI) play a significant role in this process. However, there is still limited research on how AI technology influences the experiences, perspectives, and attitudes of Pakistani ESL learners, especially those in rural areas of District Shangla.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Research Objectives

1. To analyze the Importance of AI in English language learning.
2. To identify the benefits and challenges of AI in English Language learning.
3. To explore the learners, use AI tool to learn English

Research Questions

1. What is the importance of AI in English language learning?
2. What are the benefits and challenges of AI in English language learning?
3. How do ESL learners use AI tools?

Significance of the study

The Qualitative study aims to fill the gap by investigation the Importance of AI tools (ChatGPT, DeepSeek, Gemini, Perplexity and Meta AI) among Pakistani ESL learner, especially in District Shangla. The research seeks to examine the benefits and challenges, focusing on how Pakistani ESL learner utilize these AI tools to develop their language skills. The study further aims to provide insight into the learning-oriented implication of integrating AI tools into the educational context.

Delimitation

This study the importance of Artificial Intelligence in learning of English as a second language at district Shangla, KPK, Pakistan. The participants are only undergraduate students from the Department of English at the University of Shangla, from 2nd to 8th semester. School level and postgraduate are not part of this research. The study covers only District Shangla and does not include other districts and provinces. It focused on only ESL learner and does not include native or foreign language learners. The research also considers only selected AI tools such as (ChatGPT, DeepSeek, Gemini, Perplexity, and Meta AI) while excluding other AI Language learning applications or websites. Additionally, this study follows a Qualitative method which highlights experiences, perceptions, opinion and thinking, of the students, does not include quantitative methods or Statistical Analysis.

Literature Review

The origins of Artificial Intelligence trace back to the 1950s, when researchers began working on machines capable of human-like thinking. Among the pioneers of this era was British mathematician Alan Turing, who, in his well-known paper "Computing Machinery and Intelligence," proposed the idea of machines being able to think. A couple of years, in 1956, John McCarthy gave the official name Artificial intelligence at Dartmouth Conference, an event that can be said to be the origin of Artificial intelligence as a separate field of research. In the 1970, AI become more practical with the creation of expert system, which where computer programs design to solve problems like human. Over the year, AI has improved a lot due to the growth of Machine Learning and deep learning. There are some problems with AI the need for large amount of data and concerns about privacy and fairness in how AI systems make decision. Furthermore, AI was first introduced in 1956 as the idea of creating smart machines. It has greatly improved overtime, through the 20 Century AI slowly turned into machine and software that could make decision and change their behavior by following certain rules. These systems were made to act and think in ways similarly to human. According to (Wang, 2019) the meaning of AI has growing with new technologies such as Natural Language processing, Machine Learning and Neural Network. These tools help machine do work that involve thinking, such as Learning from experience and solving problem. While (Qiao, 2021) say these technologies make AI more advanced and useful. Additionally, AI has Change many fields from heath to manufacturing. It continues to shape how we live and work. Today many industries depend on AI and other modern technologies to grow and improve. Even through AI has a long history, there is now a strong agreement that smart machine with the ability to learn, think and adjust are essential in today world these skills allow AI systems to perform tasks that are becoming more Complex often reaching result that were not possible before. That is what makes AI powerful and valuable tools (Arrieta et al, 2020).

Definition of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial Intelligence means using computers to do things that usually need human thinking. It helps in problem solving, learning new things, understand language and making decision like human. (Thneswary et al, 2024). Artificial Intelligence is transforming modern life and work by enabling devices to replicate human

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

thought, actions and behavior. Like AI can help in recognizing voices, understanding texts and solving problems. These abilities were once only possible for human. Now machine can do them. Artificial Intelligence used in many sectors which includes Education, Healthcare, Finance and Manufacturing. It helps people save time and make better decision. For students, AI can support learning by correcting grammar, ideas and translating language.

Classification of AI

Artificial Intelligence as often categorized into different levels according to their degree of intelligence, with each level serving distinct functions.

Artificial Narrow Intelligence (ANI)

Narrow Artificial Intelligence is also known as ANI, which is made to do one particular task very well. It cannot think or act outside of that particular task. For instance, Voice assistant like Siri and Alexa are design to recognize and response to spoken commands. Similarly, apps like Netflix and You tube use ANI to suggest videos that show based on user choice. However, these systems cannot work beyond the areas they are built for (Babu & Banana, 2024).

Artificial General Intelligence (AGI)

General Artificial Intelligence (AGI) refers to a form of AI capable of thinking and learning in a manner similar to humans. It would be able to understand different situations, problem solving, and apply knowledge in many areas, just like people do. This type of AI only exists in theory, No AGI system has been made yet, but researchers are still working on it as a future goal (Rathi, 2022).

Artificial Super Intelligence (ASI)

Super Intelligence AI or ASI, is a theoretical form of Artificial Intelligence that would be much smarter than human in every way. Whether in problem solving, decision making or creativity, it could think faster, learn quicker and come up with solution beyond human understanding. While ASI does not exist yet, it also raises serious concerns about how it might be controlled and what effects it could have on society (Gulchenko, 2024).

AI is Implemented Using Several Key approaches

There are several key approaches used in the implementation of Artificial Intelligence each approach plays a vital role in enabling to mimic human like intelligence and decision making.

Machine Learning (ML)

Machine learning is an AI approach that allows systems to learn from data instead of being programmed directly for a specific task. By processing large datasets, large volumes of data can be fed into these systems to enable them to draw patterns as well as forecasts. The most prevalent kinds of the machine learning algorithms are reinforcement learning, unsupervised learning and supervised learning.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN)

The writings on artificial neural networks (ANNs) are works on the working of the human brain. They consist of networks of interconnected nodes of artificial neurons enabling an AI to learn and run through a complex data pattern. ANNs are a central component of current AI deployment in such areas as natural language processing, driverless car technology, and picture recognition.

Natural Language Processing (NLP)

Natural Language Processing (NLP) involves interaction between the natural language and computers. It enables machines to comprehend, interpret and create the human language. Machine translation, chatbots and sentiment analysis are some common ways of using NLP.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Knowledge Based Systems (KBS)

This system uses a knowledge base consisting of rules or facts that have been programmed to make decisions or provide recommendations. (Nagahisarchoghaei, et al, 2023). Examples include expert systems in medical diagnosis and case-based reasoning systems.

Uses of Artificial Intelligence across different Industries

There are some examples of Artificial Intelligence which is used on different Industries in everyday life.

Health

Artificial Intelligence (AI), in healthcare, has been used in areas that help improve patient care as it may aid in medical image analysis (including X-rays, CT scans, MRIs, among others) to help produce more accurate diagnoses. AI also helps in reading and analyzing doctors' handwritten notes to avoid mistakes. Another important use of AI is in the development of new medicines through faster data analysis. It can detect serious diseases, such as cancer, more quickly and accurately than many human doctors. This is possible because AI checks patient data carefully to find signs of illness early.

Manufacturing

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is applied to in the manufacturing industry to carry out several duties automatically and reduce the number of human resources. It helps in predicting when machines need maintenance, which prevents sudden breakdowns and saves time. Besides, AI makes the supply chain more efficient as well since it tracks and handles any resources much more efficiently. Additionally, Smart Artificial Intelligence robots work quickly and precisely on assembly lines to perform repetitive tasks. These robots can also detect errors during production, which helps maintain product quality. Out-put increases while reducing waste and delays.

Finance

In the finance field, Artificial Intelligence is used to detect fraud and protect customer accounts. It helps banks and companies manage risks by studying patterns and unusual activities. AI tools also track market trends to understand how the market is moving. These tools can quickly go through large amounts of financial data. Based on this data, they give better and more accurate investment advice. This helps customers make smart financial decisions with more confidence.

Education

In the Department of Education, Artificial Intelligence is used to support personalized learning (Perdana et al., 2021). It helps teachers customize lessons based on each student's needs. AI can track student progress in real-time and spot where they are struggling. Based on this, it creates study material on the spot to help the student improve. This makes learning more effective and focused for every learner.

Ethics and Challenges in development of AI

While Artificial Intelligence provides many advantages, it also raises serious challenges and ethical issues in the development of AI. One major issue is that Artificial Intelligence driven automation might replace human jobs. There is a growing fear that, in certain industries, work once performed by humans is now being carried out by machines, which could result in unemployment and widen economic inequality. Another challenge lies in the opaqueness of AI decision-making. many AI algorithms function as "black boxes" meaning that their internal processes are difficult to interpret. This lack of transparency makes it challenging to establish trust and accountability. Particularly, when AI is applied in critical fields such as healthcare and law. Moreover, Privacy remains a central concern in AI development, especially when these systems collect and process personal data. (According to Ahmad, 2023), noted it is essential to protect user data and implement strong regulation to ensure that AI operates in an ethical and responsible manner.

Artificial Intelligence Tools for Language Learning

According to (Gonzalez Calatayud et al. 2021), with the rise of artificial intelligence, language learning has evolved through smart tools designed to meet diverse learner needs. These solutions employ, Natural Language Processing (NLP), Speech Recognition and Machine Learning to provide highly personalized and

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

adaptive instruction.

Tools for Grammar and Writing Improvement

One popular AI tool for language learning is Grammarly. It helps to users with grammar, punctuation and writing style. Grammarly checks text for mistakes and corrects them. According to (Gonzalez Calatayud et al, 2021), Grammarly enhance students writing skills, especially in college, by reducing errors and making essay clearer. Another tool, ProWritingAid, not only checks grammar but also analyzes writing style based on sentence flow and repetitive words, making it useful for learners at all levels.

Tools for Pronunciation and speaking Skills

Artificial Intelligence tools like ELSA speak use speech recognition to help learner improve their Pronunciation by comparing the user speech with that of native speakers. ELSA highlights mistake and provides feedback related to speaking and pronunciation, which helps university students speaks more fluently and develop better accents. According to (Yong, Zhang & Lin, 2022), Similar tools for pronunciation and speaking practice, such as Google Translate and Text to Speech, assist learners during speaking exercises and contribute to fluency development.

Tools for Vocabulary

According to (Gonzalez-Calatayud et al, 2021), vocabulary learning tools such as Quizlet and Memrise which used Customizable flashcards and quizzes. These apps help to learner study better and also provide repetition features to support students in retaining vocabulary related information. They are especially helpful for the preparation of TOEFL and IELTS programs.

Case Studies on AI tools in Language Learning

Studies examining the use of Artificial Intelligence tools in higher education have shown that AI can help improve language skills. A study by (Woithe and Filipec 2023) looked at how English learners used Chat-GPT for speaking practice. The results showed that students who practiced with ChatGPT for 10 weeks improved their speaking ability and built confidence compared to those students who only used the traditional classroom learning method. Similarly, a study by (Nagahisarchoghaei et al, 2023) focused on how adaptive learning tools help university students. The findings, based on applications such as Duolingo and Rosetta stone, indicated that these tools help students learn grammar and vocabulary more effectively. Students also reported greater interest in learning because the apps included game-like features, which increase motivation. Another study by (Lai & bower 2020), highlighted how AI tools contribute to group learning. they found that tools such as Google Docs, when combined with artificial intelligence outcomes, improved teamwork and enhance the quality of group projects. Students appreciated receiving quick and easy feedback from the AI, which meant they didn't always need the teacher assistance. However, the study also emphasized that teacher support remains very important in guiding the overall learning process.

Challenges and feature Directions of AI

Artificial Intelligence tools are very helpful, but they also have drawbacks. Depending too much on them can weaken students that ability to think critically and solve problems. In addition, not everyone can access these tools easily, especially in poor areas, due to high costs. (Nwekeet et, al.2023). In the future, improvements in AI will make language tools even better, as they will combine with AR (Augmented Reality) and VR (Virtual Reality) system. Learners can then experience realistic and interactive settings. These technologies can create life like situations where students practice English in natural and everyday contexts.

Students perception of AI in Language Learning

Students have different opinions about the use of Artificial Intelligence in language learning. some highlight advantages, such as it is ease of use, while other point out possible drawbacks. Since AI is becoming more common in the field of education, it is important to understand what students think and why. This awareness helps maximize the benefits of AI for both learners and instructions.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Positive Perception of AI in Language Learning

Many students find AI helpful in their studies because it is flexible and performs tasks quickly. A study of the (Huang et al, 2021), shows that college students use tools such as ELSA Speaks because they provide effective feedback on pronunciation, which help learner practice and speak English more fluently. The research emphasizes that regular use of these tools improves student confidence in speaking English. Similarly, (Perdana et al, 2021) noted that students who use Grammarly for their writing find it to be useful tool. it makes writing correct sentences easier, as the tools provides quick and clear feedback, helping learners identify their mistakes and improve through practice.

Negative perception of AI in Language Learning

In negative perception of AI that have not all students are completely comfortable with AI tools. (Nweke et al. 2023), found that some learners worry about relying too much on technology, fearing it could weaken their ability to think critically and solve problems independently. Another concern is whether AI tools are always accurate, particularly in areas that require deeper understanding, such as cultural contexts and complex grammar structures. Another study by (Uno et al, 2024) highlights that students hold different opinions about AI in grading, while some believed that AI feedback was unbiased, others doubted its ability to fairly assess subjective work, such as essays, which often require human interpretation.

Factors Influencing on Student Perceptions

There are several factors influencing student perceptions. These includes Ease of use, effectiveness, access and affordability and personalization. Each is discussed below:

Ease of Use

Students are more open to using AI tools when they are easy to operate. according to (Lai and Bower 2020), found that simple, clear design with easy to follows instructions received better responses from students.

Effectiveness

Students prefer AI tools that actually help them learn better. (Chen et al. 2020), found that when these tools clearly improve grammar, pronunciation and vocabulary skills, student are more likely to use them.

Access and Affordability

Cost and availability influence how students perceive AI tools. Those who can easily access them usually appreciate these technologies, while students with limited resources often find them out of reach or accessible only to certain learners (Zahara et al, 2023).

Personalization

Students prefer AI tools that adjust to their learning styles and provide personalized support. Smart systems that address learner specific problem areas tend to make them more satisfied. (Gonzalez- Calatayud et al, 2021).

Benefits of AI in Learning English

The integration of artificial Intelligence in education has transformed the experience of English language learning, especially for university students. AI powered tools offer personalized experiences, adapting to each learner unique needs while making progress effortless and enjoyable through playful interaction, seamless accessibility and instant feedback.

Personalized Learning Paths

Artificial Intelligence can create personalized learning experiences, which making it very useful. Some apps such as Duolingo and Ling Q track to how well user perform and adjust lesson for their needs. This helps learner focused on areas where they struggle. According to (yang et al. 2022) highlights student using AI tools improved their grammar and vocabulary scores by 25% compared to those relying only on traditional method.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

AI gives tailored feedback to each learner, helping them work on weak areas while strengthening what they already know. It also identifies learning gaps, ensuring that learners continue progressing with confidence.

Enhanced Accessibility

AI is changing the way people learn English by making it easier and more convenient. With AI-powered apps, students can learn anytime and anywhere without being restricted to a classroom or fixed syllabus. This is especially helpful for those who can't attend regular classes. Apps like Babble and HelloTalk allow learners to practice speaking English with native speakers in any time. (Chen, P., & Lin, Z. 2020). Highlights that AI tools help bridge educational gaps by providing low-cost, flexible learning opportunities, regardless of learner backgrounds, to improve their English skills.

Immediate and Actionable Feedback

Artificial Intelligence technologies are highly effective in offering prompt and accurate responses, which play a vital role in language learning. For example, some apps like ELSA speak learner improve pronunciation by giving real-time feedback, allowing them to adjust their speech immediately. Similar platforms such as Grammarly and Hemingway Editor support writing development in grammar, tone, and clarity. According to (Davis et al. 2023), learners who use AI tools for corrections experience better retention and develop skills faster than those who received traditional feedback. The quick interaction supports an active learning environment and helps learners engage with complex linguistic patterns more effectively.

Motivation and Engagement

Many artificial intelligence apps for learning include leaderboards, streak tracking, and rewards to keep learners engaged and motivated. An example is Memrise, which uses adaptive flashcards and quizzes to help users progress in a game-like format, making learning enjoyable. This helps students stay focused and remember vocabulary and grammar more effectively. (Lee & Kim, 2022) highlights university students who use syllabi to provide a refreshing alternative to traditional study methods.

The Role of Learning Experiences in AI

Artificial Intelligence is changing the way higher education works by offering helpful tools that make learning better for students. It helps create personalized lessons that keep students interested and improve learning outcomes. With artificial intelligence, the traditional method of teaching is being transformed in a new and effective way.

Enhancing Learning Experiences through AI

Artificial Intelligence is also playing a part in improving education by making the learning experience more interesting and interactive. AI tools allow learners to adjust the speed and style and enable a more individualized study experience unlike in conventional ways of teaching. For example, DreamBox and Squirrel AI use smart systems to spot what a student does not understand and offer tailored help (Homles et al., 2019). These tools keep students challenged without making them feel discouraged. AI has also made it possible to create virtual tutors and chatbots that give students support whenever they need it. These tools act like real conversations to help learners ask questions and get quick answers, which improve all learning experiences. (Chen et al., 2021).

Impact on Motivation and Engagement

AI has a strong influence on how motivated students feel during learning. One of the most effective ways it does this is through gamification, a method that makes learning fun by adding game-like features. Apps like Quizlet and Duolingo use points, badges, streaks, and leaderboards to keep learners motivated and focused on their goals. According to (Ghaffari & Haddadi, 2022), this feature makes learning feel like a game rather than a chore, helping students stay interested and consistent in their efforts. AI also encourages teamwork and group learning experiences, further engaging them. For instance, Google Docs, when combined with AI outcomes systems, allows students to work together in real time. This promotes interaction among peers. According to (Lai et al., 2020), students who worked on group tasks using AI tools felt more engaged than traditional classroom methods.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Improved Learning Outcomes

AI tools that provide instant feedback are transforming the way students learn. For examples, writing applications such as Grammarly & ProWritingAid, not only correct grammatical error but also explain why an error occurs and suggest improved alternatives. This step-by-step guidance helps learners gradually enhance their writing skills. According to (Davis and White, 2023) speaking tools like ELSA Speak allow learners to practice pronunciation by highlighting specific areas that need improvement. With consistent use, this leads to greater fluency and improve confidence in speaking English (Zawacki-Richter et al, 2019). Similarly, (Johnson et, al 2022), research argue that AI tools positively influence academic outcomes. Their study revealed that students who used AI for language learning scored, on average, 20% higher on standard test compared those who only learned through traditional classroom methods. These findings demonstrate that AI can play a powerful role in improving learner academic performance and overall language proficiency.

Challenges in Optimizing role of AI

Although AI has improved the way students learn, there are still important challenges relying too much on AI tools can weaken student ability to think critically and solve problem independently, in addition, some AI systems have built in biases, they may not provide the same learning experience. (Naghisarchoghaei, et al 2023). To make the most of AI in education, School and institutions need to address these issues carefully.

Independent Learning and Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence has greatly changed how students learn on their own. It provides helpful tools that make it easier to study independently and take charge for their learning. With AI, learners can access support that fits their personal needs and choose a study pace that works best for them. This helps build strong self-learning habits. Still, there are concerns about whether using AI too much might make students rely on it instead of thinking and problem solving their own.

Foster Autonomy through AI

AI tools help students learn on their own by giving than the chance to study without always needing a teacher. These tools, such as smart learning apps and online tutors, adjust to each student level. They help learners identify what they do not understand and focus on improving weak areas. Apps include Duolingo and Babbel allow students to practice English grammar, vocabulary and speaking in simple way. According to (Yang et al, 2021), Learning who regular and actively used these apps gained more confidence and become more active in their learning. They were able to manage their own study time and keep track of progress. Moreover, Chatbots like ChatGPT create real Conversation between human and machine, allowing students to practice speaking and writing skills. Learner do not feel afraid of being judge, which makes them more relaxed and confident. This kind of practice also helps improve their language use in life situation not just in the classroom, (Davis & White, 2023).

Risks of Relying too much on AI

AI tools offer many advantages, but depending on them too much that can be harmful. It may reduce student ability to think critically and solve problems on their own. According to (Nweke et al, 2023), AI provides quick answers and corrections, which can prevent learners from fully engaging their mind to understand and retain new information. For example, someone uses writing tools Grammarly to fixed grammatical mistake easily, they may fail to learn actual grammar rules behind corrections. Additionally, the limited human interaction in AI use creates a passive learning process, which can reduce opportunities to build strong communication skills and understand context. This highlights why AI should support traditional learning but should not replace it.

Finding the right balance

To get the most out of AI in independent learning, it is important to maintain a healthy balance. Teacher and school play a key role in guiding students on how to use AI tools wisely, without becoming AI with regular teaching methods can help develop learner autonomy while also promoting critical thinking and self-awareness (Holmes et al, 2019).

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Impact of AI on Educational Ethics and Society

The use of AI in education offers many advantages, such as personalized learning and faster access to information. However, it also raises serious ethical and social concerns. These include issues related to the safety and privacy of learner access to AI tools, as well as their overall impact on society and education, which are becoming increasingly dependent on technology.

Ethical Concerns in the Use of AI

A major ethical concern in the use of artificial intelligence in education is the protection of student personal data. AI tools often gather and process large amount of information to provide personalized learning support. However, if this data is not properly protected, it can be misused. (Holmas et al, 2021), Highlight the need for strong data protection rules and ensuring that system follow legal frameworks such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to protect student privacy. Furthermore, Security is another important issue in field of education. If hacker attacked an AI system, they could gain access to private student data, which may lead to identity theft or other harmful action. To reduce this risk, Schools and universities should implement strong Cyber security tools to keep AI system and student or learner information secure (Johnson and White, 2022). Additionally, there are ethical concerns about ensuring that AI systems are fair and transparent. If AI tools are trained on unbalanced or limited data, they can unintentionally reproduce existing social biases. For instance, a system that evaluates student performance might prefer certain ways of speaking or cultural backgrounds, which could be unfair to student from diverse communities. (Davis et al, 2023).

Social Effects of AI in Education

AI has the potential to reduce or address educational inequality, though its impact depends on how effectively it is implemented for positive outcomes. AI make quality to education more accessible for students in low source area, as platforms like Doulingo in khan academy Offer affordable learning tools that go behind distance and location (Smith et al, 2021). However, not all students have access to the internet or devices needed to use AI tools. This gap highlights the importance of making AI based education available to every student regardless of financial background. Furthermore, AI also impacts how students interact with each other. While it supports personalized and independent learning, it might minimize face to face communication and group activities. As classroom become more dependent on technology, it is important to balance social learning along said the use of AI tools (Zhao et al, 2022).

Moving Ahead

In the field of education, social and ethical considerations are very important in AI for teacher, technology developer and policy maker to works collaborative. They should create clear guidelines that support responsibilities with fairness, openness. AI developer should include ethical standard to ensure that all students have equal access to technology along said traditional methods of learning.

Previous Research

Numerous studies have examined the use of Artificial Intelligence in English education, emphasizing adaptive learning experiences, personalized learning, and the technical limitations of AI in replicating human thought. One such work, *Artificial Intelligence in Education: A Review*, applied a broad literature review approach to assess AI applications in learning. This paper was based on adaptive learning platforms, e.g., Duolingo, which deliver personalized lessons according to the needs of the learner. The findings revealed that AI tools significantly enhance personalized learning by helping students address their weaknesses and adapt to learning at their own pace. This flexibility is especially useful for learners who want to acquire language skills through specific strategies. Another Study, *Persistent Trajectory towards Proficiency: the interaction between adaptive learning and artificial intelligence in language learning*, employed a case study research design with a qualitative component. it examined the adaptive learning technology applied in English language education and highlighted the role of Artificial Intelligence based platforms like Duolingo in offering personalized learning experiences. The results indicated that AI supported adaptive language learning adjusts content to individual learner needs. These tools help students concentrate on challenging areas while keeping theme motivated through interactive and engaging activities. The third study, *Brain intelligence go*

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

beyond AI, conducted an analytical investigation into the technical limitations of AI in replicating human thinking. It focused on the cultural and contextual challenges faced by AI systems in language learning. The study found that although AI performs well in correct grammar, it often fails to understand culture references and idiomatic language. This shortcoming limits its effectiveness in providing complete and meaningful language learning experiences.

Research Methodology

The chapter describes the procedure that facilitated the research with regards to the steps involved in data collection and analysis. This research aimed to discuss the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in assisting students in second language acquisition of English. It took place in District Shangla, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan in which students in the English Department at the University of Shangla participated. In this chapter, a clear picture was given of research design, target population, sample selection, instruments, data-gathering methods, and ethical issues. It also explains the method applied in the analysis of the data collected and conclusions drawn. All the research actions done were carried out with caution and proper ethical consideration. A qualitative research design and the collection of data was carried out in the form of a structured interview. Thematic analysis was applied to analyzing the responses and highlighting their themes. This qualitative approach was taken to gain in-depth insight into students' experiences with AI in their English learning process.

Research Design

This study had chosen a qualitative approach to investigate students' real-life experiences. This design was selected to obtain an in-depth understanding of how learners engage with AI tools in the process of learning English. A qualitative design helps in collecting in-depth information. It gives the researcher an opportunity to explore how students interact with AI and what benefits or difficulties they face. It also helps to identify areas where AI is more effective and where it may not be very helpful. This kind of research provides rich data that cannot be captured through closed-ended questions or surveys. The design was flexible and open-ended, allowing the participants to express themselves freely. This helped in uncovering hidden aspects of the learning process that are often missed in other forms of research. Flowchart illustrating the qualitative research design for a study on AI in secondary English language acquisition, outlining steps from research purpose to key themes.

Target Population

The target population for this research was the students enrolled in the English Department of the University of Shangla. These students were chosen because they were already using AI tools in their learning. Some of these tools included ChatGPT, Deepseek, Google Gemini, Perplexity and Meta AI. These tools helped them improve grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, and other skills related to English language learning. The population was relevant to the research aim because these students had direct experience with AI tools. Their daily learning activities included the use of technology for educational support. Therefore, their insights were expected to be authentic and useful in understanding the actual role of AI in second language acquisition. Most of these students belonged to rural areas. They used smartphones or laptops with internet access. Their interaction with AI tools varied from using grammar checkers to practicing spoken English. Some used AI regularly, while others used it only when needed. This variation in usage also gave a broad view of different learning experiences.

Sampling Method

The research used random sampling to select participants from the population. This method ensures that every student had an equal chance of being chosen. In total, 12 students were selected for the study. This number was considered appropriate for a qualitative study because it allowed for detailed data collection while keeping the workload manageable. The students were selected based on their availability and willingness to participate. They were also chosen because they had some experience using AI tools in their English learning process. Participants included both male and female students with different academic levels, such as BS English students from various semesters. The use of random sampling helped avoid bias and ensured that the sample represented different types of users. Some participants were advanced users of AI tools, while others

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

were beginners. This mix provided a balanced view of AI's impact on English learning. Each participant was given proper information about the study. They were also informed about their right to leave the study at any time. Only those who gave their written or verbal consent were included.

Research Tools/ Scales

The main tool used for data collection was the structured interview. This method was chosen because it allowed the researcher to ask the same questions to all participants. Each interview consisted of 10 pre-designed questions. The structure helped in comparing responses and finding common themes. The interviews were conducted in person. Each session lasted between 20 to 30 minutes. The interviews were held in a quiet environment, such as classrooms or study rooms, to ensure the comfort of participants. The language used during the interviews was simple and easy to understand. The questions focused on the use of AI tools, their advantages, disadvantages, and the personal experiences of the students.

Data Collection

Data collection was done in a step-by-step manner. First, the researcher contacted the university administration to get permission. After that, a list of willing students was prepared. Then, 12 students were selected randomly. Each student was contacted personally to fix a suitable time for the interview. The participants were briefed about the aim of the study before the interviews commenced. They were assured that their information would remain confidential. No personal names or identities were used in any part of the study. The interviews were conducted face-to-face, and responses were recorded using a voice recorder or written notes. The entire process of data collection was completed in two weeks. The data was stored securely to maintain privacy.

Data Analysis

The collected data was analyzed through interviews using thematic analysis. This method was used to find patterns and themes in the responses. The process followed the model suggested by Braun and Clarke (2006), which includes the following steps:

Familiarization with Data: The researcher read and listened to the interviews several times to understand the content.

Generating Initial Codes: Important points were highlighted and labeled. Each meaningful sentence or idea was assigned a code.

Searching for Themes: Similar codes were grouped together to form themes. For example, codes like "easy to use," "user-friendly," and "accessible" were grouped under the theme "Ease of Use."

Reviewing Themes: The researcher checked whether the themes matched the data. Themes that were unclear or repetitive were revised or removed.

Defining and Naming Themes: Each theme was given a clear name and description.

Writing the Report: The final step was to interpret the themes and relate them to the research objectives.

The following major themes that emerged from the data were:

- Benefits of AI in ESL Learning
- Challenges of AI in ESL Learning
- Future suggestion of AI in ESL learner

These themes helped the researcher understand how AI tools support English learning. They also provided insights into students' feelings, emotions, and expectations from AI in education.

This chapter presented the overall research process. The study used a qualitative method to explore how students use AI tools in learning English. The population consisted of students from the English Department, University of Shangla. A total of 12 students were randomly selected. Structured interviews were used to collect data. The questions focused on the benefits, challenges, and experiences of using AI tools. The data was analyzed using thematic analysis. Key themes were developed based on the responses. All ethical guidelines were followed during data collection and analysis. The research provided deep insights into the real experiences of students, helping to understand the role of AI in modern language learning.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Discussion / Analysis

This chapter analyzes the findings of the highlighting both the benefits and challenges of Artificial Intelligence in English as a second language learning. The interview data reveal recurring theme that reflect participants perception, opinion and thinking that showing how AI contributes to accessibility, skill development and motivation while also presenting limitations concerning pedagogical depth, data privacy and classroom interaction.

Benefits of AI in ESL Learning.

The use of easy and accessibility

The majority of participants from 12 to 11 noted that Artificial Intelligence tools make learning and easier with enjoyable. Because they based on the user-friendly interface, good responses which available in every place and anywhere. Answer No (5) stated that “AI tools give accurate and precise results and save much of overtime”. Similarly, Answer (6) mentioned that “AI gives a clear and short answer, providing friendly discussion as well”.

Interpretation

The responses collected from participant highlights a consistent view about the accessibility and easy of using AI tools in English learning. Out of 12 the majority of some participants reported that Artificial Intelligence make the process of learning more easier, convenient and engaging. This showing a strong agreement among learner about the useless of AI as a supportive tool in their education journey. The result reflect that AI is not only appreciate for technological advancement but for ability to simply learning task in a user-friendly way. One participant mentioned important aspect is the user-friendly interface. The design and structure of AI tools encourage interaction without technological barriers. This is significant because the easy of navigation directly effects of confidence on learner. When student encounter tool that are simply to use, they are more likely to remine engaged and develop a positive attitude toward learning. The smooth interaction with AI also minimized frustration allowing learner focused on the content rather than on handling technology. The study also highlights the role of AI in providing in immediate and accurate responses. According to Answer no (5) mentioned that AI tools gives accurate and precis results and save time. This showing the efficiency of Artificial Intelligence impact on students in study practices. Instead of spending long hour searching for information which learner able to receive direct answers. This time saving element is not just about convenience but also about improving productivity. Student can invest the save time in practicing knowledge, reviewing lesson and engaging deeper learning activities. However, another participant (6) emphasized the value of short and clear answer provided by AI tools. This quality indicates concise explanation that help them quickly grasp concepts. Complicated and long responses are over whelm students particularly in context of second language learning.

The development of skills through AI

The most of participants reported using AI tools to improve their specific language skills, such as vocabular, reading and writing. Some students also mentioned speaking and listening to a lesser extent. Answer No (8) noted that “I have used AI tools for learning vocabulary, reading and Writing”. Similarly, Answer No (9) stated that “AI tools like ChatGPT, DeepSeek etc. help me in Reading and Lexical Collection”.

Interpretation

The responses of participants highlight how Artificial Intelligence tools are being used as a practical resource for improving language skills. The focused of most students was on vocabulary, reading and writing which speaking and listening appeared less emphasized. This difference in preference reflects the way learner prioritize skills that support academic performance and written communication. Vocabulary acquisition is essential for both reading comprehension and writing development. When student mentioned AI tools in this context, they see them not only as source of definition but also as instruments that provide synonyms in context. This indicates that learners perceive vocabulary building as the foundation of other abilities. Reading skills also appear to be supported by AI. Learner connected reading practices with the exposure to diverse texts provided by digital platforms. AI tools supply simplified explanation, translations or summaries, which

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

help students process difficult passages. This reflects a shift from traditional learning methods where student depended heavily on teachers or textbooks, to self-guided explanation supported by interactive systems. Reading becomes less of a passive activity and more of dynamic process where learner can question, clarify and verify content instantly. Writing as another central skill developed through AI. The mentioned of ChatGPT and another tool shows how students use these technologies for drafting, editing and structuring written work. Writing is often viewed as the most complex of the four language skills because it requires organization of ideas, grammar and clarity. The testimonies of students also reflect how AI influences learner autonomy. These tools like ChatGPT and DeepSeek are not only technological resources but also partner in the learning journey. They allow learner to take control of their pace, choose specific areas to practice and engage with language without time or location limit. The shift toward self-directed learning emphasized flexibility, personalization and qualities often missing in traditional classroom environment.

Motivation and Engagement

The most of participant reported that the use of Artificial Intelligence tools increased motivation and engagement in learning. This was especially due to the help, variety, explanation and interactive feedback provided by these tools. Answer No (8) mentioned that “AI tools keeps us motivated and excited to learn English everyday”. Moreover, another Answer No (10) said that “Yes, it is motivated and excited us because when we try to search one words, meta show it is synonyms, antonyms etc.”.

Interpretation

The participants responses indicate that Artificial Intelligence tools have significantly enhance their motivation and engagement in learning. This observation is important because motivation is a central factor in the success of second language learning. Learners who remain motivated are more attractive to engage with material consistently, sustain practice and manage the difficulties that naturally occur during the language learning. The participants commented reveal how Artificial Intelligence contributes to this motivation and practice way. Several participants noted that AI tools provide variety, clear explanation and interactive feedback. These features create a supportive learning environment that encourage active participation. Unlike traditional classroom methods that depend on material includes textbooks, presentation, assignments and home works, AI tools adjust to learners needs by provided immediate responses, tailored suggestion and range of examples. This flexibility helps minimized learning anxiety and improve confidence, allowing learners to approach English with greater interest and persistence. According to Answer no (8) mentioned that AI tools keep learner motivated and excited to learn English every day. This statement highlights the role of AI in promoting consistency. Daily practice is often difficult to maintain without encouragement, but AI tools appear to bridge this gap by providing learner engaging sessions that sustain their interest. In this way AI is not only as a language aid but also as a source of encouragement that progress regular learning. Another answer no (10) illustrated dimension of motivation by nothing how AI provides synonyms, antonyms and related word meanings when learner search for single term in context. This reflects the exploratory and resourceful nature of AI-based learning. Instead of offering only direct answer, the tools guide learner toward discovering broader of meaning. This process creates excitement and deepens vocabulary knowledge, making learning interactive and meaningful. From these insights, three features emerge as central to learner motivation includes immediacy, interactivity and variety. These elements explain why learner feel motivated and engaged when using AI tools.

Challenges of AI in ESL learning

AI can't replace a teacher Most of the participants (10 out of 12) strongly agreed that AI tools can serve as a supplement but not as a substitute for teachers. Answer No (5) mentioned that “AI is Artificial and will give knowledge based on cite research, web while a teacher gives you experience from day-to-day life”. Additionally, another Answer No (10) stated that “No, because AI does not have emotional intelligence and humans have”.

Interpretation

Based on the interview data, most participants show a consistent view that AI can play a supportive role in the

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

learning process but cannot replace the position of human teacher. Ten participant expressed strong agreement with this idea, which highlights a general consensus. Their reasoning reflects two important aspects the difference between information delivery and experimental learning, and the absence of emotional intelligence in AI. One participant Answer no (5) explained that AI offers knowledge drawn from sources includes Research based and online content, while teacher shares experiences that come from daily life. The distinction shows how learner view AI as a tool limited to information processing. Teacher on the other hand, offer personal wisdom, practical examples and context specific guidance that cannot be replicated by machine. The comparison points to the unique value of experimental learning in education. It also reflects the trust students place in the lived experiences of teachers, which they consider more reliable and relatable than the automated responses of AI. Another participant Answer no (10) emphasized the absence of emotional intelligence in AI. This statement brings attention to the human ability to empathize, motivate and emotionally connect with learners. Education is not only about transferring information but also about building confidence developing critical thinking and guiding personal growth. These aspects require an understanding of human emotion and social

dynamic. The response underlines a key limitation of AI while it can simulate conversation and provide answers, it cannot feel, relate or respond with genuine care. This suggest that participant see AI as a valuable aid that can increase access to information and improv learning efficiency. The teachers role extends beyond the classroom, shaping attitudes, discipline and ethical understanding which are areas where AI lacks competence.

Challenges and limitation of AI

Some participant mentioned that AI sometimes gives confusing responses, details explanation and depends on internet connectivity. Answer No (4) said that “I stopped using it because it provides extraordinary knowledge that is not necessary”. Additionally, another Answer No (7) noted that “Yes, I stopped sometime because AI provides details which are not often contrasting”.

Interpretation

The responses from the participants highlights some important challenges and limitation associated with use of AI in the learning process. One of the main concerns express was the issue of confusing and unclear response. Several participants mentioned that the answer generated by AI were sometimes complicated, vague or not directly related to their needs. This reflects a significant limitation because effective learning requires clarity, precision and context. when AI fail to provide this, it minimized the learner confidence in using such tools consistently. Another point is the problem of excessive details, noted by Answer no (4) explained that they stopped using AI because it often provides extraordinary knowledge that is not necessary. This suggests that AI is the capacity to supply a wide range of information, not all of it is suitable for learners at different stages of understanding. In some cases, an overload of details can create confusion instead of improve learning skills. This observation connects to the concepts of cognitive load in education. Irrelevant information especially when it is not directly connected to the learner. Slow down comprehension and discourage continued use of AI tools. In addition, reliance and internet connectivity was noted as a practical limitation. AI tools largely depend on online access which students face difficulties when they are in areas with weak or unstable internet. This makes AI less reliable compared to traditional learning resources includes textbooks which are always accessible without external support. The dependency highlights digital divide in education. Learner from undeveloped area struggle to benefit from AI technologies. According to Answer no (7) noted that AI responses were sometimes inconsistent, as details provided by system did not always different in ways that made sense for comparison or critical understanding. The raises questions about the accuracy, consistency and contextual awareness of AI generated content. When learners expect clear differences, contrasts and explanation but system fail to provide them, it reduces the effectiveness of Artificial Intelligence as an educational partner. Taken together, these responses reflect the confusion between the potential of AI and its practical application in real learning environments. One said AI provide access to broad knowledge and instead feedback. Another said the very lengthy information can become a burden if not carefully filtered or adapted to the learner level. Moreover, technical limitation such as internet dependency and occasional lack of contextual sensitivity minimize the trust learner place in these tools. These challenges

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

underline the importance of human guidance in the use of AI for education. Teacher, mentor and educator can help filter, contextualize and simplify the information provided by AI.

Issues about data privacy

Based on the interviews, some participants expressed concerns about personal data and security issues, which they considered very important. Answer No (7) said that “AI is a tool for blackmailing by different AI user, so I worried whenever I share my personal data”. another Answer No (8) mentioned that “Yes, ChatGPT now accesses your data and it also remembers your past data and gives you information according to that”.

Interpretation

The findings from the interviews show that data privacy is a major concern for many participants. The believed that sharing personal information with AI tools carries possible risks. According to Answer no (7) expressed fear that AI could be used as a tool for blackmailing. This concerns highlights a lack of trust in how personal data is handled and protected. Another answer no (8) mentioned that ChatGPT not only remembers past data but also uses it in future interaction. This perception created doubts about whether the system stores private details and how such information might be used later. Both responses underline sensitivity of privacy issues and the importance of securing personal data in AI based platforms. These concerns show that user do not see AI only as a neutral tool for learning or assistance. Instead, they believe it has the ability track, store and misused data. This view indicates a gap between the technical functions of AI and the way users understand them. While most AI systems are designed to protect user privacy, participants still felt that their information could be misused by other. Such fear reduce trust in technology and make people more careful when interacting with AI. It also shows that the lack of clear information about AI stores and uses data increases suspicion among user. The issue of blackmailing mentioned by one participant points to a social risk. In many societies personal data is not only a matter of privacy but also of personal safety. If people believe their information can be misused, they may avoid using digital platform. Therefore, ensuring data protection is not only a technical requirement but also factor in building trust between user and Artificial Intelligence.

Classroom VS AI learning

Most participant agreed that AI is not better than classroom learning, as they appreciated the classroom for its Content, human interaction and Emotional Intelligence. Answer No (11) mentioned that “No, it is not better than the way of learning in class because we pay full attention”. Additionally Answer No (10) noted that “No, because AI does not have emotional intelligence and human have”.

Interpretation

The view of participant shows that most of them prefer classroom learning over AI learning. They shared different reasons to support this choice but the main points were related to attention, human interaction and emotional support. For many, the classroom not only a place to study but also a space where they feel connected, motivated and guided by teacher. This sense of belonging and focus was seen as missing in AI based learning. One participant explained that classroom learning helps them to pay full attention. Responses highlights that the physical environment of a class keep student discipline and focused. In classrooms, there are fewer chances to lose concentration because the teacher supervises the learning process. On other hand, learning through AI may not always provide the same structure setting. Students can easily get distracted when learning on their own without human supervision. This shows why many learners feel that traditional classrooms are more effective in keeping them engaged. Another participant pointed out that AI does not have emotional intelligence while human do. It is a very important point because education is not only about receiving knowledge. It is also about receiving guidance, encouragement and emotional support. Teachers understand when students are confused or dis-courage they provide help accordingly. AI cannot feel emotions in the same way. It can give information but cannot understand the emotional needs of learner. This makes the classroom experience more valuable and meaningful. The answer also show that participants see education as a complete process. It is not only about personal growth and personal connection. In a class room, students interact with teachers and classmates. They learn how to share ideas, respects others and build confidence.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

These aspects of education cannot be replaced by AI focuses mainly on delivering information, not on building character and relationships to another. At the same time, these responses suggest that learners do not completely reject AI. Instead, they feel that AI cannot stand as a replacement for classrooms. It can provide information, but it cannot create the same environment of care, discipline and interaction that human teachers provide. In this way, the responses highlight the limit of AI in education.

Future direction for AI in ESL learning

Further improve AI in ESL context

Based on the interviews, participants provided further suggestions for AI in the ESL context. Participant (9) noted “AI based Essay and Article assessment tools” additionally another Answer No (8) “suggested Free English Speaking AI tools”. More ever Answer (12) said that “Offline AI tools without Internet”. Finally, Answer No (7) noted “Simplification of Complex AI Response”.

Interpretation

The participants in the study gave meaningful suggestions to improve the use of AI in English as a second language learning. Their responses show that AI is already useful, it still needs adjustment to meet the needs of learner in a better way. The idea they shared highlighted both practical concerns and the demand for more learner friendly tools. One participant suggested the development of AI based essay and article assessment tools. This shows the learners want to play a greater role in improving their writing skills. Writing is often one of the most difficult areas for English as a second language learner because it requires not only grammar but also structure, coherence and critical thinking. An AI system that can give instead feedback on these areas would help learners improve faster. It would also reduce their dependence on teacher for every draft, giving them more confidence to practice writing on their own. Another participant pointed out that the need for English speaking AI tools. Speaking is often the most challenging skills for ESL learners, especially when they do not have regular access to native or fluent speakers. A free AI tool that allows real time speaking practice would remove this barrier. It would create opportunities for learners to practice pronunciation, fluency and confidence without fear of judgment. This suggestion reflects the importance of accessibility in language learning. Many students cannot afford paid platforms so free tools would ensure equal opportunities for learner from all background. A different perspective came from a participant who emphasized the need for offline AI tools. This highlights a practical problem faced by many learners in regions where internet access is unreliable or costly. Offline tools would make AI more useful in such contexts, ensuring that student can benefit from learning supports at any time, regardless of connectivity issues. This suggestion reflects the reality that technology is not equally available to all and that inclusivity should be a goal in the design of AI learning system. Another important suggestion was to simplify the complex responses that AI some time produces. Learners feel that AI explanations can be too detailed which makes them difficult to understand. For ESL learner, clarity is essential. Simplified responses would allow students to grasp concepts more easily and apply them in practice. This show that AI can provide a lot of information, it needs to adapt its communication style to match the level of the learner. Taken together, these suggestions focused on the need for AI to become more flexible, inclusive and learner centered. The learners see potential in AI but also recognize its limits in its current form. They want tools they not only deliver knowledge but also guide them step by step in writing, speaking and understanding. They also want tools that are affordable, accessible and easy to use.

Findings

There are some findings emerged from the interview responses. Participants communicated their thoughts, opinion, expression about the importance of Artificial Intelligence in learning of English as a second language learning at district Shangla Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan. The followings are major findings based on interview responses.

AI as a Supportive learning partner

The Analysis show that most participants viewed Artificial Intelligence as a supportive tool rather than a replacement for teachers. They share that these tools include ChatGPT, Deepseek, Google Gemini, Perplexity

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

and Meta AI helpful in Writing especially in grammar, coherence and vocabulary building. AI also provide them confidence to practice English without fear of judgment. Some participants explained that AI acts like a private tutor that is always available and patient. This indicates that learners are open to using technology as a part of their language learning journey.

Traditional Classroom instruction remains the dominant paradigm in Education

Despite the usefulness of Artificial Intelligence, classroom learning remains the most trusted and preferred method. Learner valued face to face interaction, emotional connection and personal guidance. Many students said they learn better when teacher explain lesson and provide directly feedback. It also mentioned that classroom promote discipline, teamwork and communication among students. This indicates Artificial Intelligence cannot fully replace human teachers because emotional intelligence understanding and empathy are still missing in the system of AI. Inequitable Access to Digital Resources. Another finding is the issue of unequal access to AI tools. Several participants from rural or undeveloped areas said that poor internet connectivity limits their use of AI. Some could not afford paid tools or advance devices. This indicates that economic and technological inequalities still affect learning opportunities. The digital divide remains a strong barrier to equal learning for all students.

Challenges in Data Protection and Security

Participant expressed fear about how Artificial Intelligence tools handles personal data. They worried that their information could be stored, tracked and misused. A few mentioned fearing about data leaks and hacking incidents. These fears make them cautious about using AI tool for learning. It highlights the need for strict data protection and transparent privacy policies for AI applications used in digital education.

The Cognitive Burden of processing elaborate Information

From the data analysis some participants said that Artificial Intelligence give long and complicated explanation that are hard to understand. They felt overwhelmed by too much information and preferred short, clear answer. This indicates that AI tool should use simpler and student friendly language especially for English learners at the beginner level. Simplification can make learning smoother and effective which minimize the cognitive burden from human mind.

The lack of Empathic and interpersonal capabilities in AI

A repeated idea in many responses was the emotional gap in AI learning. Learners said that Artificial Intelligence cannot motivate, encourage and understand feelings the way teacher do. Human communication builds confidence and emotional support which learners continue their studies. The lack of social and emotional elements in AI creates a mechanical learning experience.

Motivation and Self-Discipline through AI

From the analysis of data a few participants reported that using AI made them more self-discipline. Since AI is available anytime, students could study according to their own schedule. They also said AI encourage independent learning because it provides instead feedback and answers. This focused on that AI can increase self-motivation and promote autonomous learning habits.

Integration of Artificial Intelligence with Human Teaching

A new insight that emerged is the desire for a blended learning model. Participants did not want to replace teacher with AI. Instead, they wanted teacher to use AI as a supportive tool in class. For examples, Artificial Intelligence could help in checking Essays, explaining grammar and extra providing examples. This integration can create a balanced approach combining technology and human guidance.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study investigates that Artificial Intelligence plays an important and growing role in English as a second language learning. The findings from District Shangla show that AI students learn in flexible, personal and efficient way. It provides instead feedback, easy access to information and motivate

through interactive features. Students used AI tools to strengthen vocabulary, reading and writing. These tools simplify learning, save time and create confidence among learner who may otherwise struggle in traditional settings. The most significant outcomes of the study are the recognition of AI as a supportive learning partner rather than a replacement for teacher. Participants made it clear that while AI explain and correct language structure it cannot teach emotions, ethics and social understanding. Teacher remains essential because they can respond to student's feelings, guide through discussion and encourage personal growth. Emotional intelligence and human connection are central parts of education that AI cannot replace. AI main strength lies in its accessibility and user-friendly design. The study identifies serious challenges. Students found that AI sometimes gives lengthy, confusing and unnecessary information. This overload can create negative impact on learner especially for beginners in English. Dependence and internet connectivity is another issue in rural regions. Many students can not access AI tool regularly because of weak signal and high data costs. These barriers limit equal access to digital education. Privacy and data security also emerged as strong concerns. Some students fears that their personal information might be stored or misused. These worries minimize trust and discourage regular use of AI system. However, another finding is that AI current focus is mostly reading, writing and vocabulary. Speaking and listening skills are less developed in most AI tools. Learner expressed interest in having free and offline AI application that can help them practice speaking and pronunciation. They also wanted simpler and clearer explanations that their learning level. These suggestions show that AI still need improvement to meet the full range of learning needs. The comparison between classroom learning and AI learning further highlights the difference between human and machine-based education. Students feel that classroom environments help them focused, discipline and emotionally supported. In class they ask questions, discuss ideas and get moral encouragement from teacher. There elements are missing in AI based learning, which is often solitary and technical. Therefore, AI should be viewed as a complementary tool that add value to classroom instruction, not as a replacement for it. The overall findings show that Artificial Intelligence can enhance learning efficiency but cannot deliver emotional or ethical education. True learning happens when knowledge, guidance and empathy work together. The role of teacher remains central in changing attitudes, behaviors and moral value. AI provide information and teacher provide understanding. When combined wisely they can create a balance and effective learning environment. Future research should continue exploring AI role in speaking and listening skills as they region are less developed. It should also investigate how learner in low connectivity areas can use offline AI tools effectively. the study is limited to a small number of participants and focused only on a few AI tools. Developers should focus on designing system that produce shorter, clearer and context appropriate response for English as a second language learner. I not only a technological tool but also meaningful educational partner.

Recommendation

Based on the conclusion the following recommendations are proposed to the use of AI in English Language education.

Recommendation for AI Developer

- Create offline feature of AI tools to solve network problems: AI should work without the internet so that users can access them even when the network is weak or unavailable.
- Includes free English Speaking Practice models for ESL learner: AI should offer free speaking practice for English learner to improve their pronunciation, speaking and fluency.
- Improve content with clarity which provides complex answer by simple: the content should be clear and explain complex ideas in simple words.
- Add feature Essay Checking and Article writing assessment with personalized learning way: AI should check essays and articles while giving personalized feedback. This will help learners improve their writing.
- Ensure transparent privacy settings with users control options: AI should clear privacy setting where users can control how their data is used.

5.1.2 Recommendation for Teacher

- Encourage students to use Artificial Intelligence as learning aids, not as replacement: Student should use AI to support their studies, but it must not replace their own thinking and efforts. Teacher should explain

this clearly.

- Integrate AI into classroom activities such as ChatGPT or DeepSeek for writing Exercises: AI tools can be part of class tasks. Use these tools for language help which make learning interactive and modern.

- Guide student to critically assess AI-generated content: students should not trust AI blindly. Teachers should train them to check facts, think critically and evaluate information carefully.

5.1.3 Recommendation for Policymaker and Institutions

- Provide training programs for ESL teachers on using AI tools effectively: Teacher should learn how to use AI tools for better teaching. Proper training will help them guide student effectively. Institution must arrange regularly training sessions.

- Promote equitable access to digital resources, especially in rural areas or regions: Digital tools should be available to all, not just for cities. Rural areas also need equal access to ensure fair learning opportunities. Governments must improve internet and technology services in these regions.

- Develop guidelines on safe use of AI in education, focused on ethics and data privacy: AI use in education must follow safety rules. Privacy and ethics should be clearly defined. Policies must protect student's data and rights.

References

1. Absari, N., Priyanto, P., & Muslikhin, M. (2020). The effectiveness of Technology, Pedagogy and Content Knowledge (TPACK) in learning. *Jurnal Pendidikan Teknologi Dan Kejuruan*, 26(1), 43-51.
2. Ahmmed, M. E. (2023). Exploring ethical challenges in AI-assisted education. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3507258>
3. Arrieta, A. B., Díaz-Rodríguez, N., Del Ser, J., Benetton, A., Tabik, S., Barbado, A., ... & Herrera, F. (2020). Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI): Concepts, taxonomies, opportunities and challenges toward responsible AI. *Information Fusion*, 58, 82-115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inffus.2019.12.012>
4. Babu, M. V. S., & Banana, K. R. I. S. H. N. A. (2024). A study on narrow artificial intelligence—an overview. *Int J Eng Sci Adv Technol*, 24(4), 210-219.
5. Chen, L., Chen, P., & Lin, Z. (2020). Artificial intelligence in education: A review. *IEEE Access*, 8, 75264-75278. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2988510>
6. Chen, L., Zhang, P., & Lin, Z. (2021). Exploring AI's role in higher education: Virtual tutors and adaptive learning. *Journal of Learning and AI Development*, 10(2), 125-139.
7. Davis, R., & White, M. (2023). Enhancing student autonomy through AI-driven tools. *Journal of Educational Technology Quarterly*, 7(1), 45-62.
8. Dekker, I., De Jong, E. M., Schippers, M. C., De Bruijn-Smolters, M., Alexiou A., & Giesbers, B. (2020). Optimizing students' mental health and academic performance: AI-enhanced life crafting. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1063.
9. Febriyanti, S. N., Anggraini, M., & Fitria, B. F. M. (2024). Digital Discourse on the ChatGPT Controversy: Reflections on the Controversial Use of Artificial Intelligence Among Indonesian Youth. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Studies*, 6(9), 01-07.
10. Ghaffari, S., & Haddadi, A. (2022). Gamification in AI-based language learning platforms: Impact on student motivation. *Journal of Educational Research and AI Applications*, 8(4), 87-103.
11. Gulchenko, V. (2024). Navigating the Risks: An Examination of the Dangers Associated with Artificial General Intelligence and Artificial Superintelligence. Available at SSRN 4941716.
12. González-Calatayud, V., Prendes-Espinosa, P., & Roig-Vila, R. (2021). Artificial intelligence for student assessment: A systematic review. *Applied Sciences*, 11(12), 5467. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app1105467>.
13. Haleem, A., Javaid, M., Qadri, M. A., & Suman, R. (2022). Understanding the role of digital technologies in education: A review. *Sustainable Operations and Computers*, 3, 275- 285.
14. Harry, A., & Sayudin, S. (2023). Role of AI in Education. *Interdisciplinary Journal and Humanity*

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

(INJURY), 2(3), 260-268.

15. Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). Artificial Intelligence in Education: Promises and Implications for Teaching and Learning. Center for Curriculum Redesign.
16. Huang, J., Saleh, S., & Liu, Y. (2021). Applications of AI-based speech recognition for language learning. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 69(3), 101-120. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-020-09837-x>.
17. Kirana, M. D., Asbari, M., & Rusdita, R. (2024). AI literacy and its impact on language learning. *Journal of Educational Innovation*, 12(3), 45-60.
18. Lu, H., Li, Y., Chen, M., Kim, H., & Serikawa, S. (2018). Brain intelligence: Go beyond artificial intelligence. *Mobile Networks and Applications*, 23, 368-375. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11036-017-0932-8>.
19. Nagahisarchoghaei, M., Cummins, L., & Karimi, M. (2023). AI and the future of education: Balancing innovation and ethics. *Journal of Modern Educational Trends*, 5(2), 23-35.
20. Ng, D. T. K., Leung, J. K. L., Chu, S. K. W., & Qiao, M. S. (2021). Conceptualizing AI literacy: An exploratory review. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 2, 100041. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2021.100041>.
21. Rathi, S. (2022). Approaches to Artificial General Intelligence: An Analysis. arXiv preprint arXiv:2202.03153.
22. Ryan, R. M., Deci, E. L., Vansteenkiste, M., & Soenens, B. (2021). Building a science of motivated persons: Self-determination theory's empirical approach to human experience .